

PRINCIPLES OF ACCOUNTING – QUICK CASES

UNIT 19: Escape Room: The Variance Vault

Author: Dr Michael Guo, University of the West of Scotland

CASE OUTLINE

The Variance Vault is an interactive activity that enables accounting students to apply and practise variance analysis. Structured as a virtual escape room, the game requires students to unlock four sequential chambers, each focusing on a different category of variance: materials, labour, overhead, and sales.

Each chamber includes:

- A brief business scenario set in a UK company context (e.g. British Manufacturing Ltd, Celtic Crafts Ltd).
- Numerical data based on exam and workplace formats.
- Tasks that involve calculating sub-variances (e.g. material price and usage; labour rate and efficiency).
- A selection tool to classify each variance as Adverse or Favourable.

Students must complete each calculation and submit accurate responses to move through the chambers. A built-in timer records performance, introduces time constraints, and supports the development of planning and coordination skills.

The final screen presents a summary of the results, including all calculated variances, classifications, and total time taken. The resource can be used during class or independently, and supports both formative and summative assessment.

The activity offers structured revision of variance calculations, supports the development of interpretation skills, and encourages collaboration in a structured group setting.

CASE RESOURCES

- Live game: <https://drmichaelguo.github.io/variance-analysis-game/>
- A screenshot of the game page is provided below.

The screenshot shows a dark-themed interface for an escape room. At the top left is a padlock icon. At the top right, a timer shows 'Time: 00:00' and 'WELCOME'. The main title is 'Escape Room: The Variance Vault' in orange, with the subtitle 'YOU'RE TRAPPED! BREAK THE CODE WITH VARIANCE ANALYSIS'. Below this is an orange button labeled 'ESCAPE THE VAULT'. A 'MISSION BRIEF' section contains the text: 'The vault's security system requires accurate variance calculations to unlock each chamber. Use your knowledge of UK accounting standards and variance analysis formulas to escape!'. Below the brief are four chambers, each with an icon and a description: 'Materials Chamber - Calculate price and usage variances for British Manufacturing Ltd', 'Labour Chamber - Analyse rate and efficiency variances for Celtic Crafts Ltd', 'Overhead Chamber - Determine overhead variances for Yorkshire Engineering Ltd', and 'Sales Chamber - Compute price and volume contribution variances for London Luxury Ltd'. A tip at the bottom reads: 'Tip: Ensure each calculation is accurate and the outcome is correctly classified as Adverse or Favourable!'. At the bottom is another orange button labeled 'ESCAPE THE VAULT'.

CASE QUESTIONS AND DISCUSSION

1. Which variance or variances were most difficult to calculate? Explain your reasoning.
2. What actions might a manager take to examine a significant unfavourable variance?
3. In what ways can variance analysis inform decision-making in a business context?
4. How did the use of a timer influence your method for solving problems and working with others?
5. Based on the feedback received, which variance formula or concept would you review next?